

Table 4. Mapping of Negative Contingencies to Literature (Extended Version)

This table shows how each identified contingency is supported, related to, or subtly reflected in prior process mining literature.

Negative Contingencies	Stein Dani et al. (2023),(2024) [30],[31]	Eggert & Dyong (2022) [9]	Syed et al. (2020) [32]	Kipping et al. (2022) [14]	Martin et al. (2021) [20]	Smit & Mens (2019) [29]	Joas et al. (2024) [13]	Zimmerman et al. (2024) [40]	Oliveira et al. (2025) [23]
Distributed Team		Shifting manpower	Collaborative Tensions.						Heterogeneous environment
Result Expectation	Expectation -Inflated Expectation -Wrong Expectation of Process Mining Support - Dealing with the reality shock	Communicating the results Doubting the results of the analysis	User-Tailoredness.	Discrepancy between the model and reality	Unclear success factors Elusive business value Misleading overconfidence Unsubstantiated expectations		Elective business value Insufficient clarification of success factors		
Data Privacy		Data privacy concerns			Restricting data privacy regulations				
IOT Data					Difficult handling of unstructured data				
Insight-Improvement Disconnection	Discovered Process - Denial - Lack of expertise - Loss of Interest	Knowledge gathering(domain) Added value	User-Tailoredness.		Missing implementation guidance Lack of trust in insights Lack of continuous incorporation	Knowledge building and knowledge-sharing	Criticality toward data-driven decisions Ambiguity in the definition of use cases	Process Domain Understanding.	Missing implementation guiding
Sharing Success Story		Added value			Fragmented solutions	Knowledge building and knowledge-sharing	Fragmented solutions		
Organizational Alignment (Ownership of the process)	Organizational Commitment - lack of top management support - change resistance	Poor documentation quality Awareness	Governance Issues. User Related Challenge	Internal resistance Commitment	Lack of management support Unclear organizational anchoring Lack of interdisciplinary and cross-functional teams Resistance to change Unwillingness to share domain knowledge		Lack of interdisciplinarity and cross-functionality in teams Lack of anchor & structurization within organizations Low-level maturity in a culture of sharing and exchanging knowledge Lack of engagement Lack of management support Lack of support	Collaboration with Stakeholders	Supporting IT management Constraints data across barriers
Hidden Task	Rework - Lack of Incentive	Outdated workflow/event data				Availability and distribution of event logs:			
Architecture Integration Choice			Technical Challenges.		Challenging (real-time) system integration Fragmented solutions	Availability and characteristics of process mining software	Fragmented solutions		Lack of IS integration